

Study of Power Loom Workers In Bhiwandi.

Kishor Hirakant Agiwale¹ Ansari Mubashera Irfan²

¹Assistant Professor, B.N.N. College Bhiwandi

²B.N.N. College Bhiwandi

Corresponding author- **Kishor Hirakant Agiwale**

Email- agiwale.kishor@gmail.com

Abstract

Power loom sector is one of the most important contributing sector in GDP as it contribute more than 2% of total GDP in India and approximately 15% to the country's export earnings. Bhiwandi is named as 'Manchester of India' as it emerged as India's largest and biggest textile industry. Because of the Prime location of Bhiwandi, as nearby to Mumbai port and international airport, as well as the climate of Bhiwandi became very helpful to emerge Bhiwandi as prime power loom Industry of India. Almost 5 lakh workers are working in this industry. And these workers are facing several major problems which affects their life.

Keyword: Power loom, Electricity, Health, Hygiene, Education, Obsolete and Outdated Technology

Introduction

Power loom sector is India's very contributing sector in term of Economy. Bhiwandi after independence emerge as Prime power loom Industry of India. Bhiwandi enjoys excellent locational advantages. Located at the crossroads of National Highway (NH) 848 or Thane- Bhiwandi road and NH-160 or Mumbai Agra highway, Bhiwandi is a perfect example of highway-led development. In addition to this, strategic Kalyan-Bhiwandi Road (NH61) connects the locality with Kalyan and Ulhasnagar and adjoining industrial belts. Also Bhiwandi is nearby to Mumbai Port and International Airport. Bhiwandi is the second largest cluster of synthetic fabric manufacturing from power looms. Bhiwandi is known for its power loom industry, which accounts for around 9.5 lakh (installed) out of 65 lakh looms in the country. Almost 6000 power loom unit in Bhiwandi majority of which is of MSMES. It gives employment to about 0.5 million people directly. And almost same numbers of people are employed indirectly. It produces turnover of Rs. 1, 24,000 Crore.

History of Power loom in Bhiwandi

Bhiwandi is a key textile Centre of western India. In early 16th Century in times of Mughals this place has been a prominent place for trade. In early 20th century Bhiwandi was dominated by agriculturists but with advent of electricity, hand looms was replaced by power loom and it became hub of textile industry in 1930's. Originally Bhiwandi was a handloom Centre. After formation of Maharashtra state it slowly converted in power loom Centre. However, there were many ups and downs but despite all the obstacles this industry provide employment to more than 15 lakh families.

Objectives:

To study the social conditions of Power loom workers.

To study the economic conditions of Power loom

workers

To highlight importance of Loom workers in development of Power loom Industry.

Social Conditions of Loom Workers

Power loom industry is mainly dominated by lower and middle class people who are generally illiterate due to their lack of skill in any other sector they usually chose to work in power loom sector. We are living in a society where pupils those who are engage in physical labour are seen as lower strata of society. They have generally no voice in social decisions, meeting and functions. Sometimes they feel lonely and want to have a circle whom they can share their miseries. Several mental pressure of work and boss i.e. Seth sometimes lead them to attempt unethical activities and become habitual consumer of alcohol.

Health Issues

Places where they work are so unhygienic and difficult to breath sometimes. There is no proper sanitation facilities for worker due to which it is common in labourers that they are suffering from Tuberculosis, Asthma, AIDS etc. due to improper treatment of these diseases it led them to die because they are economically unstable. As in a society they have no voice and image that is why most of the time people refuse to support them financially. They are physically, psychologically one of the ignored section of our society. Due to stress, Mental pressure, loneliness lead them to become habitual consumers of alcohol. Alcohol consumption is now became bigger problem for these loom workers. It just not only affect their economic condition, but also give rise to several health problems. Tuberculosis or TB and Asthma are also important disease which largely affect the power loom worker. Nano particles, unhygienic condition at workplace affect most. Study shows that large number of powerloom workers are affected because of the TB or Asthma. And still no

proper solution is been their regarding this major

health issue of power loom workers.

Person Suffering from TB,

Malnutrition

They also do not have service protection just like in formal sectors. They do not enjoy service tenure as they are being paid very low due to which sometimes they have to suffer malnutrition. Which is the foremost reason behind their underdevelopment and they have to devote 8 to 10 hour with no holiday or Friday (half day holiday) due to which their health is getting detreated day by day. However, we should recognized them as a potential state of our society as they are engage in a sector where if they would refuse to work, we have no other option but to go for expensive international brands

Migration Issue- Migration is one of the very serious issue of labours, mainly migration is for to earn money. Major Chunk of power loom labour come from Bihar, Uttar Pradesh, Bengal due to underemployment or no employment. When power

loom sector establish in Bhiwandi 1930's people got enough wage to ran their families. Migration leads to several issues such as over population, emergence of slums, unhygienic condition, and deprivation of locals from employment, health issues etc.

Education Issue - As most of textile industry in Bhiwandi is dominated by lower class people who are generally migrant from UP, Bihar and West Bengal as these states lack employment opportunities due to lack of proper education. Due to their lower and deteriorated status in society they often lack political voice also. They are refuse to have voter id and ration card etc. not because they come from different states but because of improper documentation and lack of awareness about government schemes and accessibility. As they have no voice in politics, they are easily manipulated by the upper section of society as they demanding

bribes for their petty works and mentally torture them despite the fact that they are in large number they are politically ignored. We should recognize them as potential strata of our society. Migration is one of the very serious issue of labours, mainly migration is to earn money. Major Chunk of power loom labour come from Bihar, Uttar Pradesh, Bengal due to underemployment or no employment. When power loom sector establish in Bhiwandi 1930's people got enough wage to run their families. Migration leads to several issues such as over population, emergence of slums, unhygienic condition, and deprivation of locals from employment, health issues etc. also it will give rise to conflict between local and migrant workers. As local people believe that because of the migrant workers they don't get enough employment opportunities.

Political and Economic Conditions

As most of textile industry in Bhiwandi is dominated by lower class people who are generally migrant from UP, Bihar and West Bengal as these states lack employment opportunities due to lack of proper education. Due to their lower and deteriorated status in society they often lack political voice also. They are refuse to have voter id and ration card etc. not because they come from different states but because of improper documentation and lack of awareness about government schemes and accessibility. As they have no voice in politics, they are easily manipulated by the upper section of society as they demanding bribes for their petty works and mentally torture them despite the fact that they are in large number they are politically ignored. We should recognize them as potential strata of our society. Economic condition of textile labour in Bhiwandi is poor that they have to live in inhuman conditions just to send remittances to their home. There is no holiday for them. They have to work minimum 8 to 10 hours so that they can earn sufficient wage so that their families can survive. This sector provide employment to around 15 lakh people but there is an element of uncertainty due to their minimal wage rate. Their children's are deprive of education proper overall growth etc. Due to all these problems they sometimes borrow money from moneylender at very high rate of interest. Due to which they never come out of this vicious debt trap circle. Outdated obsolete technology contribute one of the major factor behind regress and decline of power loom sector in bhiwandi. Bhiwandi power loom sector face major crises of electricity due to incomplete payment of electricity bill and theft electricity number of power looms are being closed. Bhiwandi mainly produces Swiss Cotton, Silk, Jakat, PC Cotton, Bauxi, Malmal, Khadi etc. which are of better quality and produces in a huge quantity at moderate prices that is why Bhiwandi is known as **Manchester of India**. However, government should

try to overcome these issues so that this industry can flourish further.

Solution for the problem-

For their societal image collective efforts to highlight their contribution in society should be made.

1. Proper legislation should be made to improve their socio-eco and political status.
2. Labour Laws should be implemented stringently.
3. Government should try to provide maximum hours of electricity.
4. Providing housing for migrant workers which will solve huge problem of both workers and owners (accommodation).
5. Group health insurance schemes should be make mandatory for power loom workers.
6. Regular health check-ups of power loom workers should be mandatory.
7. Reduce working hours.
8. Implementation of National pension scheme, Atal pension scheme or PF like schemes for financial security.
9. Revision of wages on periodic manner.

Conclusion:

Overall condition of power loom workers is not good comparing with other MIDC workers. Government should support the Loom Owners financially and technically to replace outdated obsolete technology with new modern technology. Modernization is an answer of through which many of the problems of power loom industry can be solve. New technology, new approach of owners just not increase the profits but also the life standard of power loom workers. Government role is also important here.

Problem exists in every sector, crises happen in every industry. Despite all the ups and downs power loom industry boom Indian market and also flooded Asian market with Indian textile. It give a hope to Indian textile industry particularly Bhiwandi that in future India will be independent of textile. It also become life line of many lakh people.

References:

1. Ghanvatkar sudhir, Bhiwandi Bayan, Akshar Manav Publication, Pune 2017
2. Bhiwandi Nijampur Nagarpalika, Shatsavntrik , 1965
3. Kulkarni Vijay Anant, Swatntrya Chalvalitil Thane, Vyas Creations, Thane 2012
4. <https://www.rbi.org.in>
5. <https://cultural.maharshtrageov.in>
6. www.msmedimumbaigov.in